
DIGITAL LEARNING TOOLS AND EFFECTIVE CURRICULUM DELIVERY IN PRIVATE SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN AKWA IBOM NORTH EAST SENATORIAL DISTRICT.

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ABSTRACT

The study examined digital Learning tools and effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District. The study was guided by three research questions and three research hypotheses. A correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 9827 teachers in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District. A sample size of 384 private secondary school teachers obtained using Taro Yamane's formula was used for the study. The researcher developed instrument used in collecting data for the study was titled "Digital Learning Tools and Effective Curriculum Delivery Questionnaire (DLTECDQ)". The instrument was structured using a four-point scale and duly validated by three experts in the Faculty of Education University of Uyo, Uyo. The Cronbach Alpha statistics was used to obtain a reliability coefficient of 0.84 for the DLTECDQ. Regression analysis statistics was used in answering the research questions and in testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study shown that virtual learning platforms, collaboration tools and assessment tools significantly predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District. It is concluded that digital communication tools significantly predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District. Recommendations made among others included; Private secondary schools should invest in reliable virtual

learning platforms to improve the organization and accessibility of instructional content and this will ensure more structured and consistent curriculum delivery across all subjects. Also, schools should adopt collaboration tools to enhance communication and teamwork among students, as this will promote active engagement and deeper understanding of lesson content. Therefore, teachers should intentionally incorporate group-based tasks and interactive activities that leverage these tools to achieve curriculum objectives more effectively.

Keywords: *Digital, Learning, Tools, Effective, Curriculum, Delivery, Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District.*

INTRODUCTION

Curriculum delivery is a central component of the educational process, encompassing the methods, strategies and practices through which planned learning experiences are implemented in classrooms and other learning environments. It represents the practical execution of a curriculum, translating theoretical frameworks and policy intentions into meaningful instruction that can influence learners' outcomes. Over time, curriculum delivery has evolved from teacher-centered approaches, where the instructor is the primary source of knowledge, to more learner-centered models that emphasize active participation, critical thinking and collaboration. Robert (2024) posited that this evolution has been driven by changes in educational philosophies, technological advancements, and shifting societal needs. Effective curriculum delivery requires a clear understanding of learners' needs, subject content and appropriate pedagogical strategies. It also involves the integration of instructional materials, assessment methods and classroom management techniques to create a cohesive learning experience (Eyo, 2022).

The importance of curriculum delivery lies in its direct impact on students' academic achievement, skill acquisition and general development. Abubakar (2025) stated that when effectively executed, it ensures that learners not only acquire knowledge but also develop critical thinking, problem-solving, and lifelong learning skills.

Conversely, poor curriculum delivery can lead to gaps in understanding, low student engagement, and poor academic performance. In many contexts, there is increasing concern about the mismatch between curriculum objectives and actual classroom practices (Ita, 2024). This mismatch may arise from factors such as rigid teaching methods, lack of instructional materials, or limited professional development opportunities for teachers. The role of assessment in curriculum delivery is also critical, as it provides feedback on the effectiveness of teaching and learning processes. Shaffer (2023) posited that the integration of technology in education has introduced new dimensions to curriculum delivery, especially with the use of digital learning tools. A digital learning tool can be defined as any electronic resource, application, or platform that supports the process of teaching and learning through the use of digital technology (Chidi, 2023). It includes software, hardware, online systems designed to facilitate knowledge acquisition, skill development, and communication between teachers and learners. These tools range from simple applications such as presentation software to more complex systems like learning management platforms and virtual classrooms. Also, Kamalipour (2021) posited that digital learning tools are often used to enhance traditional teaching methods and provide more interactive and engaging learning experiences. A digital learning tool enable access to a wide variety of educational resources, including videos, simulations and digital textbooks. In addition, they support both synchronous and asynchronous learning, allowing flexibility in how and when learning takes place (Williamson *et al.*, 2020). The use of digital tools has become increasingly important due to the growing integration of technology in education.

The concept of digital learning tools revolves around the integration of technology into the teaching and learning process to improve educational outcomes. It emphasizes the use of digital platforms to deliver content, assess learners and facilitate communication. Koffi (2023) opined that one key aspect of this concept is accessibility, as digital tools allow learners to access educational materials from different locations. This is particularly beneficial in situations where

physical attendance is not possible or practical. Another important aspect is interactivity, which helps to engage learners more effectively than traditional methods. Digital tools often include features such as quizzes, multimedia content and instant feedback that enhance understanding. Taiwo (2025) posited that digital tools also support diverse learning styles by providing various formats of content, including text, audio and visual materials. In addition, digital learning tools encourage learner autonomy by giving students more control over their learning process. Teachers, on the other hand, can use these tools to monitor student progress and adjust instruction accordingly. Also, Melgaard (2022) asserted that there are so many digital learning tools that could enhance effective curriculum delivery in schools but the outstanding ones are virtual learning platform, collaboration tools and assessment tools. A virtual learning tool is any digital platform, application, or software designed to support teaching and learning through the internet or computer-based systems. It enables students and teachers to interact, share resources, and complete educational activities without needing to be physically present in a traditional classroom (Momani *et al.*, 2023).

The concept of virtual learning tools revolves around accessibility, flexibility, and the integration of technology into education. These tools often include features such as video conferencing, interactive quizzes, discussion forums and multimedia content. Virtual learning tools allow learners to study at individual own pace and revisit materials whenever necessary. Abubakar (2025) asserted that virtual learning tools also support personalized learning by adapting content to individual student needs and progress. Virtual learning tool can be used in formal education, corporate training and self-directed learning environments. Another important aspect is collaboration, as many tools encourage group work through shared documents and online discussions, while also helping educators track student performance through data and analytics. A collaboration tool is a digital platform, software, or application that enables individuals or groups to work together on shared tasks, projects, or goals. It allows users to communicate, share files, and coordinate activities regardless of their

physical location (Ailddinoya *et al.*, 2024). The concept of collaboration tools is based on improving teamwork through technology-driven communication and cooperation. These tools often include features such as messaging, video conferencing, shared documents and task management systems. Collaboration tool help teams stay organized by providing a central space where information can be accessed and updated in real time (Kelechi, 2020). Collaboration tools also enhance productivity by reducing delays in communication and decision-making. Also, collaboration tools are widely used in education to enhance effective curriculum delivery. Awidi and Paynter (2022) stated that collaboration tools support both synchronous and asynchronous collaboration, allowing people to work together at the same time or at different times, which also makes them useful as assessment tools for evaluating individual and group contributions.

An assessment tool is a method, instrument, or digital application used to measure, evaluate, and document a learner's knowledge, skills, or performance (Kamcheong *et al.*, 2023). It helps educators determine how well students understand a subject or complete assigned tasks. The concept of an assessment tool is based on providing structured ways to gather evidence of learning outcomes. These tools can take many forms, including quizzes, exams, assignments, rubrics, surveys, and digital tests. Sharma (2020) stated that assessment tools are used to identify strengths and weaknesses in a learner's academic performance. Assessment tools also support feedback, allowing teachers to guide students toward improvement. In modern education, many assessment tools are integrated into virtual learning platforms for efficiency and accuracy (Emeka, 2024). Assessment tools help ensure fairness by applying consistent criteria when grading or evaluating work. Assessment tools can be formative, used during learning, or summative, used at the end of a learning process. It is founded on the roles of digital learning tools of virtual learning platform, collaboration tools and assessment tools in enhancing effective curriculum delivery based on the background of the study, that the researcher is motivated to conduct this present study on digital

learning tools and effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District.

Statement of the Problem

Effective curriculum delivery improves students understanding by presenting learning content in a clear, structured and engaging way. It enhances academic performance by ensuring that learning objectives are properly achieved and assessed. It also supports teachers in using appropriate methods and resources to meet diverse learner needs and promote better educational outcomes. But looking into the educational sector today is the problem of ineffective curriculum delivery which has brought about the problems of poor student understanding and low academic performance, as learners are unable to grasp key concepts or achieve expected learning outcomes, which often results in widespread knowledge gaps and reduced confidence in academic tasks. It also causes increased classroom disengagement and lack of interest in learning, since poorly delivered lessons fail to motivate students, leading to absenteeism, disruptive behavior and weak participation in school activities.

Furthermore, it creates long-term educational challenges such as low examination success rates, inadequate skill development, teacher frustration, poor curriculum coverage, inconsistent assessment practices, weak foundational knowledge, inequality in learning outcomes, limited critical thinking skills, reduced employability, poor communication abilities, lack of innovation, dependency on rote learning, increased dropout rates and overall decline in educational quality within the system. In order to solve the problems associated with ineffective curriculum delivery in schools, so many researchers have conducted studies ranging from teachers to students factors as being responsible for the challenge. The continuous existence of the problem is an indication that efforts by researchers have not yielded a significant reliable result. Could this problem be as a result of non-adoption of digital tools to promote effective curriculum delivery? The researcher in considering the roles of digital tools is enhancing effective curriculum delivery is motivated to conduct the present study

to determine the extent to which digital learning tools predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to determine the extent to which digital learning tools predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District. Specifically, the study sought to determine;

- 1.) The extent to which virtual learning platforms predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools.
- 2.) The extent to which collaboration tools predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools.
- 3.) The extent to which assessment tools predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools.

Significance of the Study

This study on digital learning tools and effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District would be of immense benefit to the students, teachers, parents, educational policy makers, school administrators and researchers. Students would benefit from the findings of the study as it would increase their exposure to interactive and technology-driven learning environments that make lessons more engaging and accessible. They will also gain from improved curriculum delivery approaches that enhance comprehension, retention, and critical thinking skills. Teachers would benefit from the findings of the study as it would enable them to learn how to effectively use digital learning tools to enhance lesson delivery and student engagement. The study will also guide them in adopting improved curriculum delivery methods that foster better understanding and academic achievement among students. To the parents, the findings of the study would be beneficial as it would enhance understanding the importance of digital learning tools in improving their children's academic experiences and outcomes. The findings will also reassure them about the effectiveness of

curriculum delivery methods used in schools, encouraging greater support for their children's education.

Educational policymakers would benefit from the findings of the study in gaining evidence-based insights into the role of digital learning tools in improving teaching and learning outcomes. This will help them formulate policies and frameworks that promote effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools. The school administrators would benefit from the findings of the study as it would enable them to understand how integrating digital learning tools can improve instructional quality and general school performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District. They will also benefit by gaining insights into effective curriculum delivery strategies that support better planning, supervision, and resource allocation. The researchers would benefit from the findings of the study as it would serve as a reference point for further studies on digital learning and curriculum delivery in similar contexts. The study will also provide empirical data that can contribute to the advancement of knowledge in educational technology and instructional methods.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study

- 1.) To what extent do virtual learning platforms predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools?
- 2.) To what extent do collaboration tools predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools?
- 3.) To what extent do assessment tools predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated to guide the study;

- 1.) Virtual learning platforms do not significantly predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools.
- 2.) Collaboration tools do not significantly predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools.

- 3.) Assessment tools do not significantly predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools.

METHODOLOGY

A correlational research design was adopted for this study. This design was considered appropriate because it enables the identification of patterns and relationships among variables, thereby allowing predictions to be made based on observed correlations. In this study, the extent to which digital learning tools of virtual learning platforms, collaboration tools and assessment tools predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools is examined. The study was carried out in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District. Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District has Nine (9) Local Government Areas and lies between Latitudes $4^{\circ}25'N$ and $5^{\circ}32'N$ of the Equator and Longitude $7^{\circ}29'E$ of the Greenwich Meridian. The area was chosen for the study due to the observed ineffective curriculum delivery in different subjects the students are taught. The population of the study comprised all the teachers in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District. According to the statistics from the Ministry of Education, Akwa Ibom State, there are 9827 teachers in the 116 registered private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District. A sample size of 384 teachers in private secondary schools was obtained for the study using Taro Yamane's formula. A multistage sampling technique was employed in selecting the sample size for the study. The researcher developed instrument used in collecting data for the study was titled "Digital Learning Tools and Effective Curriculum Delivery Questionnaire (DLTECDQ)". The instrument was validated by three experts from the Faculty of Education, University of Uyo, Uyo. Thereafter, Cronbach Alpha was used to obtain the reliability coefficients of 0.84 for the DLTECDQ. Regression analysis statistics was used in answering the research questions and in testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected is statistically analyzed using Regression Analysis Statistics in answering the research questions and in testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Data Analysis and Results

Answers to research questions and hypotheses testing are done in this section:

Research Question 1

To what extent do virtual learning platforms predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools?

Table 1: Summary of Regression Analysis of the extent to which Virtual Learning Platforms Predict Effective Curriculum Delivery in Private Secondary Schools (N=384)

Variables	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²
Virtual Learning Platforms (X)	.682	.465	.464
Effective Curriculum Delivery (Y)			

Source: Field Work (2026)

Table 1 shows the extent to which virtual learning platforms predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools. The coefficient of correlation (R) of .682 shows that virtual learning platforms predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools to a moderate extent. Also, the coefficient of determination (R²) value of .465 indicates that virtual learning platforms predict up to 46.5 percent variation in effective curriculum delivery. This result shows that virtual learning platforms predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools to a moderate extent in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District.

Research Question Two

To what extent do collaboration tools predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools?

Table 2: Summary of Regression Analysis of the extent to which Collaboration Tools Predict Effective Curriculum Delivery in Private Secondary Schools (N=384).

Variables	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²
Collaboration Tools (X)			
Effective Curriculum Delivery (Y)	.719	.517	.516

Source: Field Work (2026)

Table 2 shows the extent to which collaboration tools predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools. The coefficient of correlation (R) of .719 shows that collaboration tools predict effective curriculum delivery to a high extent. Also, the coefficient of determination (R²) value of .517 indicates that collaboration tools predict up to 51.7 percent variation in effective curriculum delivery. This result shows that collaboration tools predict students' effective curriculum delivery to a high extent in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District.

Research Question Three

To what extent do assessment tools predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools?

Table 3: Summary of Regression Analysis of the extent to which Assessment Tools Predict Effective Curriculum Delivery in Private Secondary Schools (N=384).

Variables	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²
Assessment Tools (X)			
Effective Curriculum Delivery (Y)	.819	.671	.671

Source: Field Work (2026)

Table 3 shows the extent to which assessment tool predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools. The coefficient of correlation (R) of .819 shows that assessment tools predict effective curriculum delivery to a very high extent. Also, the coefficient of determination (R²) value of .671 indicates that assessment tools predict up to 61.7 percent variation in effective curriculum delivery. This result shows that assessment tools predict effective curriculum delivery to a very high extent in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District.

Hypotheses Testing

Research Hypothesis One

Virtual learning platforms do not significantly predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools.

Table 4: Regression Analysis of the prediction of Effective Curriculum Delivery in Private Secondary Schools by Virtual Learning Platforms (N=384)

Model	Sum of Square	DF	Mean square	F	Sig	Remarks
Regression	453.337	1	453.337	3.100	.000	Significant
Residual	37498.913	382	145.910			
Total	37952.250	383				

. = Significant at .05 alpha level. Source: Field Work (2026)

The results of Table 4 shows that the p-value of .000 is less than .05 at 1 and 382 degrees of freedom and at .05 level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis which stated that virtual learning platforms do

not significantly predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools is rejected. Therefore the researcher concludes that virtual learning platforms significantly predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District.

Research Hypothesis Two

Collaboration tools do not significantly predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools.

Table 5: Regression Analysis of the prediction of Effective Curriculum Delivery in Private Secondary Schools by Collaboration Tools (N=384).

Model	Sum of Square	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig	Remarks
Regression	382.529	1	382.529	2.31	.001	Significant
Residual	42423.471	382	165.070			
Total	42806.000	383				

. = Significant at .05 alpha level. Source: Field Work (2026)

The results of Table 5 shows that the p-value of .001 is less than .05 at 1 and 382 degrees of freedom and at .05 level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis which stated that collaboration tools do not significantly predict effective curriculum delivery in public secondary schools is rejected. Therefore the researcher concludes that collaboration tools significantly predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District.

Research Hypothesis Three

Table 6: Regression Analysis of the prediction of Effective Curriculum Delivery in Private Secondary Schools by Assessment Tools (N=384).

Models	Sum of Square	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig	Remarks
Regression	552.182	1	552.182	3.1029	.000	Significant
Residual	45734.532	382	177.955			
Total	46286.714	383				

. = Significant at .05 alpha level. Source: Field Work (2026)

The results of Table 6 shows that the p-value of .000 is less than .05 at 1 and 382 degrees of freedom and at .05 level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis which stated that assessment tools do not significantly predict effective curriculum delivery in public secondary schools is rejected. Therefore the researcher concludes that assessment tools significantly predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District.

Findings of the Study

From the Findings, it was observed that:

- 1.) Virtual learning platform significantly predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools.
- 2.) Collaboration tool significantly predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools.
- 3.) Assessment tool significantly predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result of the first hypothesis shown that virtual learning platform significantly predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District. This is achievable because virtual learning platforms provide structured, accessible, and consistent channels for distributing instructional content. They enable teachers to organize lessons, assignments, and assessments in a centralized system, which improves planning and coherence. These platforms also support multimedia resources such as videos, simulations, and interactive quizzes, making learning more engaging and easier to understand. Through real-time communication tools, students can interact with teachers and peers, fostering collaboration and immediate feedback. The findings of the study is in lined with the submission made by Robert (2024) submitted that virtual learning platforms enhances effective curriculum delivery in institution of learning. The result of the second hypothesis shown that collaboration tool significantly predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial

District. This is possible because collaboration tool enhance communication and interaction among students and teachers. Collaboration tools create opportunities for group discussions, peer learning, and knowledge sharing, which deepen students' understanding of subject content. By using platforms such as Google Classroom and Microsoft Teams, teachers can coordinate tasks and provide timely feedback, ensuring that learning objectives are consistently met.

These tools support synchronous and asynchronous engagement, allowing students to participate actively regardless of time or location constraints. The outcome of the study is in agreement with the submission made by Ita (2024) that collaboration tools predict effective curriculum delivery. The result of the third hypothesis shown that assessment tool significantly predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District. This is achievable because provide measurable evidence of how well students are achieving learning objectives. When teachers use structured assessments such as tests, quizzes, and assignments, they can identify gaps in students' understanding and adjust instruction accordingly. This continuous feedback loop helps ensure that the curriculum is not just covered but actually understood by learners. In many private schools, assessment tools are aligned closely with curriculum standards, making them reliable indicators of teaching effectiveness. The findings of this study is in agreement with the submission made by Chidi (2023) that assessment tools significantly predict effective curriculum.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study reveal that virtual learning platforms significantly predict effective curriculum delivery in private secondary schools by improving access to instructional materials and enhancing teaching efficiency. Collaboration tools also emerged as important predictors, as they foster communication, teamwork, and active student participation in the learning process. In addition, assessment tools significantly contribute to curriculum delivery by enabling

continuous evaluation and timely feedback on students' academic progress. Moreover, the study concludes that the integration of virtual learning platforms, collaboration tools, and assessment tools creates a more effective and responsive educational environment in private secondary schools. These technologies collectively support improved teaching strategies, student engagement, and data-driven decision-making. Therefore, their adoption is essential for achieving consistent and high-quality curriculum delivery.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that:

Private secondary schools should invest in reliable virtual learning platforms to improve the organization and accessibility of instructional content, and this will ensure more structured and consistent curriculum delivery across all subjects. Consequently, teachers should be provided with regular training and technical support so they can effectively integrate these platforms into their teaching practices. Schools should adopt collaboration tools to enhance communication and teamwork among students, as this will promote active engagement and deeper understanding of lesson content. Therefore, teachers should intentionally incorporate group-based tasks and interactive activities that leverage these tools to achieve curriculum objectives more effectively. Private secondary schools should implement digital assessment tools to continuously monitor students' academic performance, since this will provide accurate and timely data on learning progress. As a result, educators should use the insights gained from these tools to give prompt feedback and adjust their instructional strategies to improve overall curriculum delivery.

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